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**INTERCULTURALITY – AN ASPECT OF TEACHING ROMANIAN
LANGUAGE IN AN INTERACTIVE WAY**

Nowadays the act of communication is an important part of our life including all its aspects: family, work, friendship. In linguistics the communication is a set of actions that have in common the transmission of information as messages, news, signs, symbolic gestures, written texts and others ways of communication between two or more persons, called interlocutors, or more formally, transmitter and receiver. This kind of communication must not be confused with the communication devices called the transmitter and the radio receiver, which is used in telecommunications.

The concept of *communication* is closely connected with our existence as humans, and then as a society, due to the fact that human beings and communication are interdependent. It is a dynamic process, constantly changing. The society owes its existence to human communication. It means that the human community is viewed as a process that involves the participation of all members of the society in the process of communication. The communication is represented in different forms, but we would like to discuss the media communication and mass communication, which is a form of media communication, intended for large population, and may have a subjective form (which aims to manipulate public opinion) and an objective form (aims to simplify the informing of people). Mass communication is an integral part of the social media, a relatively new concept, which has developed especially in the post-war period, as a direct consequence of the emergence of new forms of sharing information, either through radio waves or through small-screen images. Dale Carnegie said: "There are only four ways in which we come into contact with others. We are evaluated and catalogued through these types of interaction: what we do, how we look, what we say and how we say it" [3], these must be the purpose of a teacher too, the teachers must know what to say and how to say.

The educational process represents "the main subsystem of the education system, in which the training activity organized according to the education objectives that orients the training-development of the student's personality takes place" [2].

Teaching a foreign language is more than learning the grammar or assimilating a large number of words. Ioan Cerghit emphasizes that "the strategies sketch the variety of ways to achieve the wanted goal and have the value of some working tools of studying." [1].

The current educational theories place the student in the center of the educational act and recommend starting the educational process from the student's centers of interest in order to motivate him to learn the taught language. Approaching a "chalk-board" method of teaching (which had its advantages), has also its disadvantages, for example, the passive student as a participant to process does not seem to be appropriate for today's generation.

The teachers use a wide variety of strategies and methods that encourage the active participation of the student in the activities during the lesson. Learning by “doing”, bringing real life problems into the classroom and helps students to discover the required information to solve these problems, these methods set the student in the center of activity and it represents a part of the student centered learning approach. The teacher guides and facilitates learning, rather than controlling it, helping students to interpret and organize their knowledge is an important part process of education. The main goal is to develop skills not only in the studied content but also in the learning process itself. An active teaching-learning process is important because it has a greater impact on students using modern methods and strategies.

Within the Romanian language as a target language class, we can experience different teaching-learning strategies and methods, using one method or another depends on the chosen approach. In our opinion there are a lot of ways of sketching a perfect lesson, for example: Person-Centred Approach, Communicative Approach, The Silent Way, Suggestopedia, Community Language Learning, The Total Physical Response Method. For applying a modern strategy we need a lot of materials and tools as:worksheets, pictures or flashcards, picture stories, posters, brochures, leaflets, CDs, DVDs, games, poetry, plays, role-plays, projects. For an effective teaching-learning act it is good to alternate the types of teaching materials. Modern teaching techniques that are based on the Theory of multiple intelligences using exercises that resort to musical / rhythmic intelligence, visual / spatial intelligence, bodily / kinesthetic intelligence, which requires all areas of the brain efficiency to the training act.

One of efficient method is *The Direct Method*, which has refered to totally different lessons, taught exclusively in the target language. Mimicry and gestures are beginning to be used to communicate the meaning of words and structures, understanding being verified by exchanging questions and answers between teachers and students. The direct method, which appeared as an answer to the translation method, was opposite to the first one by the fact that it is prohibited the use of the mother tongue during the lesson, the assimilation of vocabulary and grammatical elements was inductive and the main objective was communication in the foreign

language. This method largely reflects social changes and the need to adapt language learning to specific contextual needs.

The Listen-Repeat method uses the exercise as a technique. The method of studying is stressed on the repeating the structures which the teacher involves until the student will not reproduce the context in a correct way. A typical lesson always starts with a dialogue, focusing on the form or structure of the language and not on the content. Teaching is invariable from simple to complex. The correct pronunciation is encouraged from the first lessons of Romanian language; the vocabulary being relatively limited. At the beginning of teaching Romanian as a foreign language the main purpose of the teacher was to prevent mistakes. Now the main purpose of teachers is to eliminate the language barriers.

In order to facilitate the process of studying the Romanian language, together with our colleagues, we have developed various teaching materials adapted to the needs of medical students. The purpose was both to familiarize them with the basic norms of the grammar of the Romanian language, as well as to assimilate the specialized terms. This didactic support is a good working tool, because it helps students to go through and to be in touch not only with the notions of morphology and vocabulary, but also those of spelling and the formation of correct, oral and written speeches. These materials will help students to overcome the difficulties encountered in studying Romanian as a foreign language, facilitating a complex understanding of language facts and developing communication skills, which will make it possible to participate properly in a conversation, expressing their opinions clearly and fluently.

The method Test - Teach - Test is a method used when the teacher wants to check if students have knowledge of a particular subject. In the initial phase, the teacher tests the knowledge on the subject, then clarifies and presents the meaning, form, pronunciation, register, so that he can finally use the knowledge testing through new types of exercises. A simple example of how this innovative method can be applied is the activity in pairs of the type "propose advices for a healthy digestive system". The teacher controls and notes the vocabulary and structures for expressing advice, agreement or disagreement. Based on the obtained results, he

could decide which area of the vocabulary or structure should be upgraded and he could choose appropriate teaching materials.

Simulation or impersonating in one situation is another extension of the method of learning through communication and involves the interpretation by the students of a role (doctor, patient), in a situation in which they must use the Romanian language (for example a situation in the hospital). The studying through communication proves that innovation can only change from learning about language to learning to communicate through that language. Focusing on working in pairs or groups can create problems for certain groups, for certain learners, especially adults, who feel that speaking in a foreign language to other native speakers is an obvious waste of time. But there is another interesting activity that makes the students to be actively involved in the debate of a topic.

The learning method by performing some tasks assigns the focus to the activities carried out using the target language, starting from the assumption that the students assimilate new words and structures while trying to express or understand what the other participants in the learning process are saying. Thus, students are given the opportunity to use the full range of skills at the same time and not within separate lessons, as was the case with the communicative method.

The conclusion drawn from this paper is that the way of teaching has been influenced by a wide variety of methods and trends. These are nothing more than a part of the process of discovering what is good and essential in the educational process, a process that is in continuous developing.

All facts about educational process has a lot of benefits because nowadays we know more about teaching and learning than we knew 50 years ago and the role of the learner has been integrated into this process. Some teaching methods such as translation, the use of a situation to demonstrate the meaning of a word or the exercise have lost their importance in modern teaching. At the same time, teachers had to keep track of with the latest trends in teaching, opting for the ones that are appropriate for them and their students.

A modern and successful teacher must, first of all, put the creativity and the critical way of thinking to be the key of didactic efficiency. Successful learning of

the Romanian language cannot be a problem in choosing a certain teaching method or technique. In the field of teaching Romanian, there are researchers who claim that a notional or communicative structural approach would be the only way to the ideal speakers where all students speak Romanian perfectly and pass the exams without any difficulty.

Didactic knowledge is scientific in nature and is characterized by teaching - learning activities, accompanied by systematic assessments as premises for regulating and optimizing the educational process, which can be regarded as a system with self-regulation [4].

The truth is that each teacher, after a certain period of time, develops their own working method after carefully checking the various existing techniques. He will, of course, adopt the one that suits not only him, but also the subject he teaches or the student body he works with.

References:

1. Cerghit, I. Sisteme de instruire alternative și complementare. Structuri, stiluri și strategii. Editura Aramis, Bucuresti, 2002, p. 273.
2. Cristea, S. Studii de pedagogie generală. EDP: București, 2004, p. 38.
3. Dale Carnegie. Cum să comunicăm eficient. Litera: București, 2019, p.34.
4. Jinga, I; Istrate, E. Manual de pedagogie. București: Editura All, 1998, p. 183.